

CERTIFICATE OF RECOGNITION

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Doreen Festo

This certificate is awarded for attending the Basic Research workshop conducted in hybrid mode in Kyiv Medical University, Katowice, Poland

Awarded March 2nd, 2024

Dr. Indraneil Mukherjee

Dr. Indraneil Mukherjee

Founder & Chairman

Dr. Palak Dutta

Dr. Palak Dutta

Founder & Chief-
Organiser

Dr. Rohit Ganduboina

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Founder and Speaker

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*MOHAMMAD
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Lord Owusu afrifa

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